

WAYS OF DEMONSTRATION OF SUGGESTION SKILLS OF FUTURE PEDAGOGICAL TEACHERS

Shermatova Manzura

UBS pedagogy and psychology
teacher of the department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14054817>

Annotation: in this article, future pedagogic teachers will help to reveal the forms, nature and structure of suggestiveness skills, the content of the concepts of suggestiveness, the essence of suggestiveness skills, not only describing their structure, but also the characteristics of manifestation. , the main theoretical and methodological rules that help to determine the connection and connection with other professional pedagogical qualities are discussed

Keywords: suggestiveness, competent, suggestive competent, suggestive ability, perceptive, gnostic, communicative

In recent years, serious reform of the education system in our country, bringing the quality and efficiency of education to a higher level, professional competence of future specialists, including teachers of pedagogy, and its composition the main task is to raise the suggestive competence of the teacher to a higher level, to introduce modern methods of improving the suggestive competence of future pedagogic teachers. The essence of today's education policy is "to make our young people who think independently, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, and who can compete with their peers in any field in the world" "to grow into independent people" 2, "to increase the effectiveness of education by creating a new, modern method of teaching the science of pedagogy" 3, including higher education professors-teachers of their countries are faced with the task of training mature personnel who love and appreciate their field, have knowledge, skills and professional abilities. In the theory of world pedagogical education, suggestive competence, in particular, suggestive competence, which is its basis, in the education of competent and competitive personnel corresponding to international standards, the future Organizational-pedagogical processes of improving suggestive competence in teachers, improvement of suggestive competence, theoretical knowledge about suggestiveness, awareness of suggestive actions, quality of performed suggestive actions, manifestation of suggestive competence in a new situation and being able to explain it to others have important scientific, theoretical and practical significance proven.

Recently, the problems of modernization of the pedagogical education system, adaptation of its methodological structure and search for effective educational

technologies have become especially urgent. The changes taking place in the life of this country - the strengthening of negative trends in the economy, social sphere, culture and education, "Weakening of the school's pedagogical immunity to growing negative social phenomena" [62, pp. 87-112]. In this regard, the role and importance of the future teacher's professional literacy and skills, his spiritual and moral qualities, and the sense of responsibility for the consequences of his activity will increase significantly. Guyot was the first to develop and justify a number of rules related to the theory of suggestibility: 1) the importance of the authority to exercise influence; 2) influencing communication with confidence; 3) the need to accept and share ideas that should be instilled in others; 4) the power of influence depends on the tone of voice, which is enhanced by facial expressions. Expanding the concept of authority necessary for a pedagogue, he emphasizes that it can be based on three elements: 1) love and respect, 2) the habit of obedience, 3) fear. It argues that the first of these three grounds should be preferred. "You need to love the child now and then, and then you don't need to punish him, because ... love always begets love, and this feeling is the most powerful and main engine of education" [32, p. 124].

The main theoretical and methodological rules that help to reveal the essence of suggestive abilities, not only describe their structure, but also help to determine the characteristics of their manifestation, their connection and their connection with other professional pedagogical qualities:

1. Consideration of influencing skills as an element of general pedagogical training;
2. Description of the management system through the step-by-step algorithm for solving pedagogical problems. Viewing our problem through the prism of these theories allows us to avoid one of the common misconceptions in pedagogical research - the separate description of a group of necessary skills without connecting them with other elements.

The formation of professional qualities is common to future teachers occurs during pedagogical training. The general pedagogical training of the teacher is educational lessons on pedagogical sciences and pedagogical practice is the process and result of teaching students in the system, and is characterized by a certain level of development of the teacher's personality, the formation of general pedagogical knowledge, skills, and qualifications [18, B.4].

Through suggestive skills, we understand the totality of the teacher's professional mental and practical actions, he is required to form the child's

views and attitudes to the world around him, to activate the processes of self-management and self-education. allows him to use the occult and thereby change and correct any aspect of his mind and behavior.

Explaining the totality of the teacher's professional intellectual and practical actions through suggestive skills, to help him to form the student's views and attitudes to the world around him, to activate the processes of self-management and self-education. that it allows the use of influence and thus the possibility of changing and correcting any aspect of the student's mind and behavior is explained and the following author's tariff forms: "Suggestive skills in students designed to evoke positive emotional states. The indicator of these skills is the word of the teacher, which is the activity of students and penetrates into the spiritual-ethical nature of their relationship, and the influence carried out in mutual relations is connected with other professional and pedagogical skills: organizational, communicative, perceptive, gnostic, etc., to the developing personality of the student has an integral effect". In conclusion, we emphasize that all of the above allows us to conclude that the ability to influence is a complete component of the professional training of a future teacher. Their structure is a set of mental and practical actions, which are based on the influencer's mechanism of influence. These actions correspond to a number of pedagogical skills, they allow working in activities and require special, targeted training.

References:

1. Jo'raev R.H., Ibragimov X.I. Pedagogik jamoaning innovatsion faoliyati. // Xalq ta'limi jurnali. – 2004. - №2. – B.4-8.
2. Jo'raev O'T. "Irodaviy faollikning vaziyatli va shaxslilik determinantlari" magistrlik dissertatsiyasi Toshkent, 2016 yil.
3. Zayniddinova M. Talabalarning mustaqil fikrlash faoliyatini takomillashtirishomillari. //Xalq ta'limi, 2004. 1-son. 132–135-betlar.
4. Zufarov SH. Ta'lim muassasalariga innovatsiyalarni joriy yetish tizimini takomillashtirish – pedagogik muammo sifatida // Formirovanie intellektualnogo, tvorcheskogo i duxovnogo potentsiala lichnosti obuchayushixsya v sovremennyykh usloviyax. Sb.nauch-met.stat. v 24 chastyax. CH.6. – T., 2009. S. 59.

